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Nestin activation during *Listeria monocytogenes* infection *in vitro*.

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Nestin has developmental functions and functions in the CNS which are perturbed in cancer. We demonstrate here activation of *NES* in the host cell during infection with *Listeria monocytogenes*. Nestin has major functions in cancer and in the immune system during infection.

Citations

1. Kumar, Y. and Valdivia, R.H., 2008. Actin and intermediate filaments stabilize the *Chlamydia trachomatis* vacuole by forming dynamic structural scaffolds. *Cell host & microbe*, 4(2), pp.159-169.

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